

Impact of Internet Technology on the Social Behavior Issues among Children in Al Batinah Governorate During 2020-2021

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ABSTRACT

The Internet is a recent boom that occurred in all societies, and it has many advantages such as the ease of finding what we want easily and without effort and fatigue, Internet can help people to learn. In the present times the use of internet and its applications have increased among young children. Our study attempts to review the negatives and risks of child addiction to the Internet, especially in Al Batinah Governorate, and what are the issues and challenges that exist and what are the solutions to eliminate social behavior issues in children?

Our findings show that the negative impact of internet technology on a child can be reduced through effective family care, integrating the child into society, and helping the child make friends.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The Internet has many advantages that it provided to people, but also there are disadvantages to this fierce technology that left nothing to the features except and devoured it, as we see many problems that the Internet causes, especially for children before adults, many children are entering the world of the Internet more closely to addiction, Some families may ignore this problem, thinking that the Internet has great benefits for children as it is a distinct source of information and education. However, children spending long hours in front of the Internet without awareness or control makes them vulnerable to deviation and may put them in big problems.

It is also considered a negative social technology that helps to keep people apart, because the more hours people spend on the Internet, the less they communicate with their families, and the less their circle of acquaintance becomes. Also, the increased use of this technology, may raise feelings of psychological frustration and loneliness. Un monitored use of social media among children have led them into the dangers of being victims of cyber-bullying, cyber-dating violence in teenagers, sextortion, sexting, online dating, catfishing [10][11].

In a most recent study made by Li. Y in 2022 [8] identified how teenagers are affected by the use of smart devices. They reported that the boom in social media networks have much addicted children of this teen age and they are almost glued to their devices. This has a negative impact on them and increases cybercrime

in the society. It is obvious to say that parent hold the greater response in monitoring the children before they go out of control. A research in Greece [9] was made to focus the perception of parents on various social media applications and online games children are exposed to.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

We live in a time when the internet has become available in all things around us, and it is very easy to use. On the other hand, the internet is the gateway to an endless world of good and bad things at the same time. It is very important to know its risks and study them to reduce and avoid them, so we will try to find out how the Internet can affect the child's social behavior.

1.2 Framework

Figure 1 presented below shows how children's lives are affected by overusing internet technology and specially the social media apps and games. It is a hard truth that not all games found on the Web, Android and iOS are suitable for children of every age.

Figure 1. Child's use of Internet technology and it's impact

When internet is used by children and they are left unmonitored, this leads to loss of control over time that the child in engaging himself/herself over the internet [5]. This causes various issues in the social behaviours. Figure 2 shows the main negative factors that would impact on children's social behaviour.

Figure 2. Reasons for the negative effects of using the Internet on children's behavior

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The Internet technology has made our life look easier than it was before, with its many advantages, but using the Internet in the right way is very important. Some children do not know how to use the Internet in a correct way, for example, they continue to watch some movies or play, so using the Internet a lot has negative effects and there is a lot of research that confirmed this, we will show you some of them [6].

According to Aiman El Asam, Muthanna Samara and Philip Terry [1], 83% of people between the ages of 12 and 15 own a smartphone and 99% use the Internet for approximately 21 hours per week, which has increased the risk of addictive behaviors on the Internet that negatively affect psychological development. They used a questionnaire to study how the internet affects in terms of age. We will bridge the existing gap, which is how to get rid of the negative behaviors caused by some games and films for children by preventing them from entering some sites through a system that prevents this except with the advice of parents or by paying a financial fee to enter in order to ensure that the person who uses the site is an adult. Also, in this research is considered accurate at some ages, but it did not refer to the age of less than 12 years old, so it is possible to study the age that were not mentioned in this research.

Tonya M. Palermo, Anna C. Wilson [2], in their research, they dealt with the fact that children under the age of 17 who use the Internet and social networks have fewer social skills. Children with heavy exposure to screens exhibit similar social skills trajectories compared to children with little exposure to screens. The results represent a challenge to the dominant narrative that social skills are declining due to technological change. The authors fill that gap by comparing teachers' and parents' evaluations of children's social skills among children in the Early Childhood Longitudinal Study 2009 cohorts. Therefore, we will try to study the forms of social decline that have not been investigated in depth.

Another idea, M. Valcke, S. Bonte, B.Ed. Wever [3], they studied how to define and activate parenting techniques to study the effect of actual Internet use for children at home. Where they found that the highest child usage level is perceived when parents adopt a permissive parenting style; the lowest level is observed when parents adopt an authoritarian Internet parenting style. Because of the different Parenting styles, the Internet has affected in a different way the thought and behavior of the child. The theoretical and practical implications and directions for future research are discussed.

Also, Jeffrey P. Harman, Catherine E. Hansen [4], found that predicted that children who misrepresent themselves on the Internet would have less well-developed social skills, lower levels of self-esteem, and higher levels of social anxiety and aggression. As well as it was found that children who reported the most faking behavior on the Internet (e.g., pretending to be older) had poorer social skills, lower levels of self-esteem, higher levels of social anxiety, and higher levels of aggression. In this research we will try to find out the average age at which these problems appear.

After research confirmed the negative effects of the Internet in order to reduce it, or at the very least, increase parents' awareness of the need to pay attention well, scrutinize the large amount of data flowing through the Internet, and make the correspondence transmitted through the international network of the Internet specializing in what is beneficial and good for children, by blocking Abusive and harmful sites poison a child's thoughts and divert their correct attitudes.

3. RESEARCH METHOD

Children grow up in a world surrounded by various media that can be easily and easily accessed. Parents may find it difficult to keep up with the rapid development of new content, features, and applications that are constantly being introduced [7].

This research will be carried out in two phases:

Phase-1 – A Survey will be conducted to collect the opinions of the parents and know various information from number of hours their children use devices connected with internet to type of applications or programs that they use.

Phase-2 – Based on the results of the survey, a smart application will be developed that will continuously monitor the usage of activities by children and will take measures to help the child from getting into a condition that is not good for them. Some of the measures taken will be:

This system will have a “Child-Mode” Enable/Disable by parents before giving any smart device to their children.

If a child is using a game/application for more continuously, a “Screen Alert” will be displayed in the main display after every 15 Mins.

If the child is continuing to use the device even after 2 or 3 alerts, then a message will be sent to the parent.

Even after sending warning to parents, if the child is using the device, then auto child-lock facility will be enabled, which can be disabled by parents only.

Repeating / Continuous “Key-Press” will also be counted, like if the child is using DEL key or BACK key repeatedly, “Screen Alert” will be sent, and the display will be locked for few minutes for the child to take rest before using the device.

4. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

As one of the research methods is towards getting information from parents of children of modern age, the researchers have floated 8 questions to parents in Al Batinah Region. The questions were floated online and there was good response from many parents. Within a week almost 143 parents from different parts of AL Batinah region volunteered to answer to the questions sent to them.

Based on the answers provided by parents we are presenting the following analysis:

It is evident that most people who overuse mobile phone has become very nervous about you and other. The Figure 4 describe the statistics of children who has become very nervous it found that 27 among 143 parents responded with “5” which is “**Strongly Agree**”, 50 parents responded with “3” which is Neutral” and 14 parents responded with “1” which is “**Strongly disagree**”.

Figure 4 – Nervous problem in children who use internet.

It became clear to us through the questionnaire that we did it to the parents about the extent to which the child isolated himself while using the phone, and we found from the Figure 5 that 42 out of 143 parents “strongly agree” with this and that there are fewer than 22 who “strongly disagree” this thing.

Figure 5 – Isolate's problem in children who use internet.

Also, we can know through the data collected that more than half of the parents who answered the questionnaire noticed a change in their children's behavior after spending long hours on the Internet, where the percentage of parents who answered. "Strongly agreed." was 26 percent in addition to 32 percent. Who answered "agree", this represents 58% of the total percentage of respondents to the questionnaire, i.e., 101 out of 143 people, and this shows us the strong influence of the Internet on children's behavior.

Figure 6 – Noticed strange behavior in children who use internet.

Some of the strange behaviors observed by parents on their children is that most of these children were quarreling with their siblings over the phone over the Internet, with 45% answering “strongly agree” and 24% “agree”, which is 69% of the total percentage. , In addition to that 62 out of 143 people answered that they noticed that their children suffer from sleep problems after using the Internet a lot, as they answered “strongly agree or agree”, and this shows us how the Internet can affect children's behavior, which in turn may affect the physical health of the child.

Figure 7 – Sleep problem and differ with others problem in children who use internet.

Parents always suffer and complain about the lack of focus and distraction of their children, especially during the first years of study, and this is what we reached through the views of the parents, as we saw that 31% suffer from this problem and a very small percentage 12% did **“not agree”**.

Figure 8 – Lack of focus and fugue problem in children who use internet.

In the figure shown below, there is a convergence in the ratios between **“strongly agree”** and **“strongly disagree”**, and because electronic friendship through social media does not positively affect the child's personality and growth, just as true friendship showed, and through the questionnaire it was found that most children, by 31%, I do not prefer online friendships.

Figure 9 – Making friends problem in children who use internet.

This is what we have ascertained through the parents' opinions that the child is enthusiastic and prefers to use the phone more than playing with the children around him, and we found that 69% **“agreed strongly”** to that.

Figure 10 – Child excited to use the phone “internet” more than play with others.

5. SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

SUMMARY:

Our study deals with the effect of the Internet on children in an attempt by the researchers to determine the effect of the Internet on children. What prompted the researchers to address this topic, noting that there are a large number of children abandoning their normal lives, games, physical activities, and using the phone frequently even in family gatherings and others? In this study, the researchers used a number of data collection tools, including a questionnaire for a number of parents and teachers. A data collection form was applied to more than 143 children. The research community is Al-Batinah North, this site was chosen for the large number of parents who suffer from this problem among their children.

The study found the following results: That children sitting for long hours affects their physical and mental health and leads to weak relationships within the family and rebellion against parental and school authority.

Acquiring violence: The child may acquire violence as a result of watching some films that present scenes of violence in one way or another, or through games that include wars or killings. The child is usually affected by what he watches and even tries to practice it in real life.

Autism and isolation: Technology pushes the child to autism and isolation from his family and friends and involves in a virtual electronic world, so you find that he spends hours in front of the TV or iPad screen either to watch movies or play games so that the child prefers to spend most of his time with electronic devices instead of spending his time with his family.

CONCLUSION:

This research tried to identify how the child uses the home Internet and to reveal some of the characteristics of this use, its fields and its implications on the child and the satisfaction it achieves because the Internet has a great impact on behavior and behavior. Thinking of children, either positively or negatively, according to the way it is used, as the random use of the Internet is far from parental control, it causes many bad consequences. But what we found through the study is that a very large percentage of parents do not care about the importance of child supervision or do not have a background about the danger of the Internet on them. What is reflected in the child's behavior and psychological state, such as the organized use of the Internet that takes place under the supervision of parents according to each age group; It will make the Internet an advanced medium in the hands of parents. It helps them build the child's personality, not destroy it, and one of the best solutions to avoid the dangers of Internet content for children is for parents to choose content appropriate for the child's age.

RECOMMENDATION:

After all of that we came out with the following suggestions and recommendation:

1. Parents should not give their children under 12 years old a mobile phone.
2. If the child needs to use the mobile phone, for something necessary like attending his online classes, he can use one of their parents' mobile phone.
3. In case that a child uses a mobile phone, the period of his use of the mobile phone should not exceed two hours.
4. Parents should try to involve their children in recreational activities such as clubs playing football or basketball, horseback riding, and many other things.
5. Parents should make time for their children to go out and play with them thus reducing the free time of the child who is likely to use the mobile phone.

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